

MISSION

eMISSion-free HV and MV transmissiON switchgear for AC and DC

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D3.1: Technical requirements for the HVAC pilot installations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is the deliverable 3.1 for the Horizon Europe project MISSION, contract no. 101135484, with a duration of four years starting on January 1st, 2024.

One key objective of MISSION is to develop and demonstrate a 420 kV AC SF₆-free circuit-breaker using vacuum interrupter and synthetic air insulation. This work is essential to prepare the interdiction of SF₆ for voltage levels higher than 145 kV in 2032, as required by new F-gas Regulation (EU) 2024/573, adopted on 7 February 2024.

The SF₆-free HVAC circuit breaker (CB) will be developed, and type tested in the laboratory by Siemens Energy (SE). To demonstrate the capacity of the circuit breaker and the compatibility with the network, this model of circuit-breaker will be installed in real grid by RTE in France and Statnett in Norway. The preparation of the project, as well as return of experience, will be shared with transmission system operator (TSO) partners in MISSION project (RTE, SN, 50Hz, REE). The experience of pilot projects will be public for other TSOs by deliverables of WP7 (pilot in Norway) and WP8 (pilot in France).

Experiences gained by this project will be useful for manufacturer to improve the design, but also for other TSOs for prepare the insertion of SF₆ free technology on 420 kV grid.

INTRODUCTION OF WP3 “TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR THE HVAC PILOT INSTALLATIONS”

A circuit breaker is a key component for the safety and reliability of the electrical grid. Circuit breakers must be capable of making, carrying, and breaking currents under normal circuit conditions, but also making, carrying and breaking currents under specified abnormal circuit conditions such as those of short circuit.

Due to its important role, a circuit breaker must be compliant with different international standards. Main standards used in EU countries are defined by International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). To be installed on the network of a TSO, the circuit breaker must also be compliance with all national regulation, which can be specific to each country.

In IEC international standard, such as IEC62271-100 [1], many options are available. Before the commissioning of pilot projects, it will not be possible to carry out all the type tests with all possible parameters. The first task of WP3 is to define minimum requirements that a circuit breaker must fulfill to be put on the network in France and in Norway before the end of MISSION Project. In the second time, it will be necessary to define parameters that cover most of the market needs and the majority of applications where SF₆-free circuit-breakers will be installed. The input for this task will come from the TSOs (RTE, SN, 50Hz, REE), SINTEF and with confirmation of feasibility by SE.

In the second task, a specification will be defined for the two pilot projects (WP7 “Pilot 1 – AC 420 kV CB in Norway” and WP8 Pilot 2: HVAC 420 kV CB in France”). The leaders of WP7 (SN) and 8 (RTE) will make a proposal for approval with contributors. The outcome of task 2 will be a list of recommended parameters for pilot sites, such as temperature range, wind, humidity and short-circuit current. A list of parameters to be monitored during the pilot projects will also to be defined, such as recording of short-circuit during pilot, quality of gas, quality of vacuum, transient voltage monitoring, switching performance monitoring etc. This planning and definition work will be led by RTE, with contributions from all WP participants. This task will provide input to WP7 and WP8.

This third task of WP3 is to define long-term planning for the pilot projects and the responsibility of each partner. The transmission network is critical infrastructure and the planning of outages for installation and commissioning of equipment is very important. The planning is usually done in two steps: long-term planning (several years before project) and detailed planning (generally one year before). At the end of this task, a long-term plan for the two pilot projects, with responsibility of each partner will be defined.

1. DEFINITION OF TYPE TESTS TO BE DONE BEFORE INSTALLATION IN A REAL NETWORK

Two main international standards applied for circuit breakers are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Main international standards applied for AC circuit-breakers.

Standard	Title
IEC 62271-1	High-voltage switchgear and controlgear - Part 1: Common specifications for alternating current switchgear and controlgear.
IEC 62271-100	High-voltage switchgear and controlgear - Part 100: alternating-current circuit-breakers

A circuit-breaker is considered to fulfill its minimum function if it passes type-test listed in Table 2. The first two prototypes delivered for WP7 and WP8 must have at least a rated continuous current of 4000 A and a rated short-circuit breaking current of at least 50 kA.

Circuit-breakers available on the market usually have a mechanical endurance class M2 (10 000 operations). Considering the first two applications, it is acceptable for the first two prototypes to have a mechanical endurance M1 (2000 operations).

Table 2: Mandatory type tests.

Category	Parameter / Success criteria
Dielectric tests	As 7.2 of IEC 62271-100 for 420 kV
Resistance measurement	As 7.4 of IEC 62271-100
Continuous current tests	As 7.5 of IEC 62271-100, with continuous current (I_r) at least 4000A
Short-time withstand current and peak withstand current tests	As 7.6 of IEC 62271-100, with short-time current at least 50 kA
Additional tests on auxiliary and control circuits	As 7.10 of IEC 62271-100
Mechanical operation test at ambient temperature	As 7.101.2 of IEC 62271-100 for class M1
Terminal fault tests	As 7.102 to 7.107 of IEC 62271-100, rated short-circuit current (I_{sc}) at least 50 kA

Considering the first two applications for 420 kV in France and in Norway (overhead line switching and for outdoor substation), the first two prototypes must also pass additional following type tests listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Necessary type-test to cover two pilot projects.

Category	Parameter / Success criteria
Radio interference voltage (RIV) tests	As 7.3 of IEC 62271-100
Verification of the protection	As 7.7 of IEC 62271-100, with IP55 class
Tightness test	As 7.8 of IEC 62271-100, with a leakage rate lower than 0.5% per year.
X-ray radiation test	As 7.11 of IEC 62271-100
Low and high temperature tests	As 7.101.3 of IEC 62271-100 with following criteria: - 50°C to cover low temperature in Norway and +40°C to cover hot condition in France
Short-line fault tests	As 7.109 of IEC 62271-100, with short-circuit current at least 50 kA
Out-of-phase making and breaking tests	As 7.110 of IEC 62271-100, with out of phase capacity of 25% of I _{sc} .
Single-phase fault test	As 7.108.2 of IEC 62271-100 for Effectively earthed neutral systems
Line-charging current breaking tests	As 7.111 of IEC 62271-100 for class C2. This test is necessary to cover the direct overhead line application for two pilot projects. Capacitive voltage factor of $k_c = 1.4$ p.u. must be proven to cover capacitive switching in presence of single phase or two-phase faults (Annex J of IEC 62271-100)

Short-circuit tests should be validated with a complete pole (one phase, consisting of two chambers), so not in a half-pole configuration. This is important in multi-break vacuum breakers because of the interaction of the high vacuum post-arc charge with the grading capacitors. This could distort the even distribution of transient recovery voltages by the grading capacitors [2].

2. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PILOT SITE (WP7 AND WP8)

To cover both climatic conditions, it is recommended to create a synergy between WP7 and WP8 by following strategy:

- For WP7 (pilot in Norway), the CB should be installed in a cold region.
- For WP8 (pilot in France), the CB should be installed in a hot region.

For application, direct connection to overhead line seems to be the best application to validate the two pilot projects. For overhead line applications, the probability of fault is considerably higher than at other applications in a substation. This strategy allows to have some return of experience when the CB has to clear a fault in real service conditions. Moreover, the strategy of rapid auto-reclosing is usually applied for overhead line, which can be an interesting operating condition for the circuit-breaker.

If the planning of the project allows, Statnett is also interested to test the circuit breaker on a shunt reactor application. This application is the most severe use-case for the vacuum circuit breaker, for the reason of multiple re-ignitions in vacuum. It is also very severe for mechanical endurance of CB, as the CB is operated daily to connect/disconnect the shunt reactor to the grid. However, it does not seem to be realistic to realize the shunt reactor switching type test acc. to IEC 62271-110 [3] before the end of the project. Furthermore, the application of shunt reactor switching might be possible for the second generation of 420 kV vacuum CBs only and might therefore not be possible in these very first pilot applications.

The real short-circuit level of two pilot sites should not be higher than 50 kA. Substations feeder with short-circuit current level up to 63 kA could also be identified. If the real results of type test done in WP4 “420 kV HVAC LT vacuum circuit breaker” validate the short-circuit level 63 kA, it will be possible to install the product on a 63 kA application to validate the higher performance of equipment.

The normal service condition for the two pilot sites should be verified and should be in the range defined by IEC 62271-1 [4] standard.

- For the pilot site in France, the ambient air temperature does not exceed 40 °C and its average value, measured over a period of 24 h does not exceed 35 °C.
- For the pilot site in Norway, the ambient air temperature does not drop below -50°C.
- Solar radiation does not exceed a level of 1 000 W/m² for both pilot sites.
- The altitude of pilot sites should be lower than 1000 m.
- The ambient air may be polluted by dust, smoke, corrosive gas, vapors or salt, the pollution does not exceed site pollution severity class (SPS) “heavy” as defined by IEC TS 60815-1:2008.
- For pilot site in Norway, ice coating should not exceed 20 mm.
- The wind speed for both pilot sites should not exceed 34 m/s.
- If the humidity level of pilot site is considered higher than normal, auxiliary voltage of 230 V AC should always be available in the substation to power anti-condensation circuit inside circuit breaker.
- Vibrations due to causes external to the switchgear and controlgear or earth tremors do not exceed the impact of vibrations caused by operation of the switchgear itself.

- It is recommended to replace an existing SF₆ circuit breaker in a substation by SF₆-free circuit breaker, in order to demonstrate the compatibility of footprint with existing substation.

One of the objectives of MISSION project is to follow the operation of the developed vacuum circuit breaker in real service condition. To maximize the benefits of WP7 and WP8, it is recommended to have some minimum recorders and monitoring equipment:

- Fault recorder: it should be possible to record the waveform of current and voltage for each phase during a fault. Values of short-circuit current cleared by the CB, as well as fault clearing time can be deduced from recorded waveform. This fault recorder should be triggered by protection system, when trip signal is sent to the circuit-breaker. It should be possible to compare the fault clearance of SF₆ free with equivalent SF₆ breaker.
- Since short-circuit current interruptions are very rare events this might not fully sufficient to determine the CB performance in general. Hence, the normal capacitive current switching operations should also be evaluated. This strategy will give data about CB in both conditions: fault clearance and normal operations.
- As reported in the literature [5] [6], the switching behavior of vacuum circuit-breakers (VCB) compared to SF₆ circuit-breakers shows significant differences. Differences between vacuum and SF₆ have been observed in pre-strike behavior, re-ignition behavior, chopping current, rate-of-rise of dielectric strength (RRDS), rate-of-decay of dielectric strength (RDDS), di/dt interrupting capability, post arc current and contact erosion. Hence the use of high-voltage vacuum circuit-breakers might potentially result in different electrical stresses on the connected assets. Therefore, pilot projects should also study all potential impacts of the new technology on other assets in the network. The use of a continuous transient voltage measurement and evaluation system is recommended in order to verify the switching performance of the high-voltage vacuum CB and to determine the electrical stress on the grid assets (e.g. over-voltages, re-ignitions ..).
- Gas density alarm recorder: when circuit breaker exposed to leakage, gas density inside the chamber drops over time. When the gas density gets below the alarm threshold, alarm signals will be sent to control and protection system. In order to have return of experience on possible leakage, the two pilot sites should be able to record at least all the alarm of gas density. As an option, it will be even better to have a permanent gas monitoring system, which can record the gas density in a permanent way.
- On site X-ray monitoring system: vacuum interrupter is well known to emit some small quantity of X-ray in some specific conditions. Before installation on site, X-ray emission is already verified in laboratory condition, as one of type test listed in table 2. To complete laboratory measurement, it is recommended to realize a permanent site monitoring real emission in service condition. Monitoring of the vacuum breaker emission can be done by using at least two passive dosimeters, using accumulating method. The first is installed inside the circuit breaker cabinet, which measures the emission around the circuit breaker. The second passive dosimeter is installed sufficiently far from the circuit breaker (at least 50 meters) and measures the natural radiation (noise). The difference between the two ones represents the net emission by the vacuum circuit breaker. Dosimeters must be renewed every 6 months. Installation of passive dosimeter can be realized as present by Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Recommendation for installation of on-site X-ray measurement.

- Online monitoring system: it is possible to equip the circuit breaker with an online monitoring system to follow operating time, opening and closing coil status, etc. This online monitoring system can give some extra information about the breaker for an exhaustive monitoring. For pilot project, online monitoring can be considered as an option, but not mandatory. Most of parameter can be deduced by fault recorder system or the transient recorder used for the transient voltage measurement.
- Large bandwidth transient recorder: vacuum circuit breaker might generate some high frequency transient during switching. Some phenomena, such as multiple reignition of vacuum interrupter is reported. If vacuum circuit breaker is installed on a shunt reactor application for a pilot site, it is important to have a large bandwidth transient recorder, which is able to record the real image of the transient. For overhead line application, transient voltage measurement is also highly recommended in order to evaluate the capacitive switching performance (re-ignition behavior, re-strike occurrence, voltage escalation, switching performance, interrupting failures, evaluation of phase dependencies, switching performance over long-term, capacitive switching performance after fault clearing, ..).
- Long term aging of vacuum interrupter: vacuum interrupter is designed as sealed for life. Experiences in medium voltage shown a quite good lifetime of vacuum interrupter [6]. It is still necessary to observe the long-term behavior of vacuum interrupter at higher voltage levels. After a period of observation of at least 10 years of service, if possible, take out one phase to control vacuum quality in the factory. The contacts surface, which can strongly influence the switching performance, should also be evaluated.

3. ORGANISATION OF THE PILOT PROJECTS (WP7 AND WP8)

To install a CB inside a substation, engineering work is necessary. It is necessary to anticipate the civil work before the delivery of CB to be able to respect the planning of MISSION project.

Any contractual discussion during engineering phase will take time to solve. In order to respect the planning, it is necessary to clarify the responsibility of each partner since the beginning. The responsibility of each partner is defined in Table 4.

Table 4: Responsibility of each partner for pilot projects (WP7 and WP8)

Task	Statnett (WP7)	RTE (WP8)	SE (WP4)
Provision of passed type test reports			X
Production of two CB for two pilot projects, factory routine test and routine test report			X
Delivery on site (one substation in France and on substation in Norway)			X
Reception on site, packages unloading	X	X	
Storage on site before installation by following recommendation of SE	X	X	
Documentation necessary for commissioning (drawing, wiring diagram, installation manual)			X
Authorization (if necessary) for starting of installation of CB	X	X	
Preparation of civil works and necessary auxiliary voltages	X	X	
Installation, commissioning tests, commissioning test report of the circuit breaker			X
Installation, commissioning tests and commissioning of monitoring system (if applicable)	X	X	
Connection of the CB to the network and to control and protection system	X	X	
Data collection for return of experience	X	X	
Return of experience report	X	X	

4. RECOMMENDATION FOR FINAL PRODUCT

The first two circuit breakers delivered in the scope of the MISSION Project can be considered as the first milestone to demonstrate the feasibility of vacuum technology at 420 kV. The product is type tested to cover the need of some substations in France and in Norway. The next step should be optimization of the design to cover as much as possible the need of European and worldwide market.

Specifications of TSOs member of MISSION project have been collected. Collected data are shown in Table 5.

Each TSO can have some specific requirements and/or other requirements to be considered. Some of those requirements are not covered by standards but are necessary to integrate the new circuit-breaker to the grid. The standard product might sometimes need to be adapted to answer to requirement of each client. This adaptation and homologation process should be taken into account to match the phase out of SF₆ in 2032. Those specific requirements are shown in Table 6.

Table 5: Collection of specifications from 4 TSO for future 420 kV live tank circuit breaker application.

Task	TSO1	TSO2	TSO3	TSO4	Necessary requirement to cover the market
Minimum and maximum ambient air temperature [°C]	-25 to +40	-50 to +30	-30 to +40	-25 to +40	-50 to +40
Pollution Class	d	e	e	e	e
Seismic Withstand	No	N/A	No	Yes	Yes, following IEC 62771-300
Rated voltage in kV (420 kV is standardize rated voltage by IEC, but EU grid code allow up to 440 kV) [kV]	440	420	440	435	440
Rated insulation level (420 kV is standardize rated voltage by IEC, but EU grid code allow up to 440 kV)	IEC 62271-1, but should cover 440 kV conditions	IEC 62271-1	IEC 62271-1 for general case. 550 kV for specific applications (ex. Statcom)	IEC 62271-1	IEC
Rated continuous current [A]	4000	At 40°C: 4000 At 30°C: 5000	5000	4000	5000
Rated short-circuit breaking current (I _{sc}) [kA]	63 or 40	63	63	63 or 50	63
Rated short-time withstand current (I _k) [kA]	63 or 40	63	63	63 or 50	63
Rated peak withstand current (I _p) [*I _k]	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.5	2.7

Rated duration of short-circuit (tk) [s]	1	3	3	1	3
Rated operating sequence	O-0.3 s-CO-1 min-CO	O - 0.3 s – CO - 3 min-CO	O-0.3 s-CO-3 min-CO	O- 0.3 s- CO- 1 min- CO	O- 0.3 s- CO- 1 min- CO
Rated out-of-phase making and breaking current [% of I_{sc}]	25	25	25	25	25
Voltage factor for out-of-phase making and breaking test	2	2	2	2	2
Rated capacitive currents and restrike class	C2	C2	C2	C2	C2
Rated line-charging breaking current [A]	400 (with kc=1.4)	400 (with kc = 1.4 at 440 kV)	400 (with kc = 1.4 at 440 kV)	400 (class C2)	400 (with kc = 1.4)
Rated cable-charging breaking current [A]	400 (with kc=1.4)	400 (with kc = 1.4 at 440 kV)	400 (with kc = 1.4 at 440 kV)	400 (with kc = 1.0)	400 (with kc = 1.4)
Rated single capacitor bank breaking current [A]	Standard value by IEC	400 (with kc=1.4 at 440 kV)	400 (with kc=1.4 at 440 kV)	Standard value by IEC	400 (with kc = 1.4)
Rated back-to-back capacitor bank inrush making current	Standard value by IEC	20 kA / 4250 Hz	20 kA / 4250 Hz	Standard value by IEC	20 kA / 4250 Hz
Rated inductive switching current [A]	315 (IEC 62271-110)	100 – 315 (as per IEC 62271-110)	100 - 315 (max 2.0 p.u. overvoltage factor)	100 – 315 (as per IEC 62271-110)	100 - 315 (as per IEC 62271-110)
Controlled switching (for specific applications)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Endurance class					

Mechanical endurance class	M2	M2	M2	M2	M2
Electrical endurance class	E2 per IEC 62271-310	E2 per IEC 62271-310	E1	E1	E2

Table 6 : Collection of special requirements of four TSO participants in the MISSION project.

Task	TSO1	TSO2	TSO3	TSO4	Possible common specification
Switching Times / break time [ms]	< 40	< 100	< 50	< 40	40
Closing Time [ms]	< 200	< 100	< 150	< 120	< 100
Opening Time [ms]	NA	< 100	< 30	NA	
Pole Discrepancy – closing [ms]		<5	< 5	< 5	<5
Pole Discrepancy – opening [ms]		<2	< 2	< 3	<2
AC voltage across open CB at 0 bar gauge pressure of insulating medium [kV]		242	254 (for at least 8 h)		
Transformer limited fault switching capability - T10		Uc = 873 kV / t3 = 46 μ s / RRRV = 19 kV/ μ s	Uc = 873 kV / t3 = 46 μ s / RRRV = 19 kV/ μ s		
Transformer limited fault switching capability - T30		Uc = 679 kV / t3 = 36 μ s / RRRV = 19 kV/ μ s	Uc = 679 kV / t3 = 36 μ s / RRRV = 19 kV/ μ s		
Static terminal load		As per IEC 62271-100 > = 3 kN in each direction	> = 3 kN in each direction	As per IEC 62271-100 > = 3 kN in each direction	
Dynamic terminal load	> = 6 kN in each direction	> = 6 kN in each direction	> = 6 kN in each direction	> = 6 kN in each direction	

Wind load zone [m/s]	34	34	≥ 25	≥ 39	
Ice load zone [mm]	≥ 10	20	≥ 10	≥ 10	
Operation altitude [m]	< 1000	< 1000	< 1000	< 1000	
Insulator material		Only composite grey color	Polymer / composite only	Polymer / composite only	
Grading capacitors (voltage control elements)	Accepted	Accepted	Mandatory	Mandatory for shunt reactors switching	
Overpressure device / rupture disc		Not mandatory	Mandatory	Not mandatory	
Secondary control voltage [V _{DC}]	48 or 125	220	220	125	
Secondary voltage for anti-condensation/heating [V _{AC}]	230	220	230/400	230/400	
Heating power per cubicle [W]		One fixed: 10, One with a thermostat: 25	100		
Auxiliary contacts (NO = normally open, NC = normally closed)	4 NO/ 4NC	6 NO/ 6 NC for CB position (2 NO and 2 NC for spring position)	9 NO / 9 NC / 1 WA	12 NA - 15 NC	
Filling valve connector		DN20	DN8	DN20	
Amount of filter material / dryer material [years]		≥ 25	≥ 40		

5. CONCLUSIONS OF WP3

In this report, the specification for the development of the first prototype (WP4) and for the pilot projects in Norway (WP7) and in France (WP8) have been defined.

Considering the short development time for the MISSION project, only some mandatory requirements have been defined in the first step. The product is considered ready to be installed on pilot sites when the minimum requirement defined in Chapter 1 of this document have been finished.

The two TSOs who will host the two pilot projects should identify substation site following criteria defined in Chapter 2. To gain as much as possible the return of experiences, Chapter 2 also recommend some record and monitoring measure to be integrated into the pilot projects.

To avoid possible conflicts during the pilot phase of MISSION project, Chapter 3 defines the tasks to be considered, as well as the responsibility of each partner before and during the pilot phase. Some of the tasks should be anticipated to minimize risks during the planning of the project.

Chapter 4 presents requirements collected from four TSO participants in the MISSION project for future 420 kV SF₆-free circuit breakers. This study will allow manufacturers to prepare industrialization of the vacuum circuit breakers before the phase-out of SF₆ at 420 kV voltage level from 2032.

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